

FFPE samples

Targeted RNA-seq by HTG
Edge-Seq

GeneID	Sample1	Sample2	Sample3	...	SampleN
PosCon1					
PosCon2					
PosCon3					
PosCon4					
NegCon1					
NegCon2					
NegCon3					
NegCon4					
Gene1					
Gene2					
...					
GeneM					

HTGQC

shinyHTGQC